

Society Sync

An Innovative Way to Design Society Management Software

Surabhi Pathare
Dept. of Information Technology
Vidyalankar Institute of Technology
Mumbai, India

Vaishnavi Pingale
Dept. of Information Technology
Vidyalankar Institute of Technology
Mumbai, India

Nidhi Singh
Dept. of Information Technology
Vidyalankar Institute of Technology
Mumbai, India

Akshay Loke
Dept. of Information Technology
Vidyalankar Institute of Technology
Mumbai, India

Abstract:- This paper discusses about the study of “Society Sync” website/Application for housing society management making the residential societies function more efficiently. In the traditional method of managing the housing society more of paper work is being involved and there is no proper assurance or security about the data which is being provided to every housing society by the residents. Also, there is no centralized management for storing the data which can also create confusion within the committee members which lacks in transparency not only between the committee members but also with the residents. There are many more limitations and disadvantages to it leading to dysfunctional society. Society Sync helps to overcome such limitations, the Society Sync is a web-based application designed to manage and streamline the operations of a housing society. The system is divided into three modules: Admin, Resident, and Security. The admin module is designed for the society's administrative staff to manage and oversee the day-to-day operations of the society. The Resident module is designed for society residents to interact with the system and access various features such as online bill payment, maintenance requests, facility bookings, etc. The Security module is designed to help security personnel monitor, visitor management, etc. The system aims to provide a secure, efficient, and transparent platform for all stakeholders in the society, enhancing the quality of life for residents and ensuring effective management of the society's resources.

Keywords:- Society Sync, Web-Based Application, Residential Communities, User-Friendly Interface, Hassle-Free, Reporting Tools, Efficiency.

I. INTRODUCTION

In society, manual labor is typically used for all tasks that take place in society. There is no automatic mechanism in place to let its members know what is going on. All the society's expense reports are kept on paper by the chairman of the organization. It also includes laborious work to create bills and distribute them to each society member. Occasionally, bills are not delivered to members, and this is

not documented. It is a major duty in society to collect payments and takes a lot of work to notify society members or send them additional communications. A system that can resolve all the issues is therefore required.

The way residential communities are administered has been completely transformed by the innovative society management software known as ‘Society Sync’. It is a platform that runs in the form of a website and application and provides several features to simplify community management tasks like communication, upkeep, and security. Small apartment buildings to big gated communities—all have different demands, and Society Sync is made to cater to them all. It represents a step towards increased transparency in societal operations and digitization. It can help a housing or flat community go paperless, promoting environmental sustainability while preserving class and security [1].

II. NEED OF STUDY

Residential communities now have society management software installed as a necessary component since it offers effective ways to handle a variety of tasks, including security, maintenance, and communication. As a result, this study's objectives are to examine the need for improved society management software and to offer alternatives to improve its efficacy and efficiency.

The effectiveness of society management software as a tool for residential communities has been demonstrated, although it still has significant drawbacks. The current program, for instance, could not be intuitive, making it challenging for non-technical consumers to utilize. In addition, a lot of software solutions have a small feature set and fall short of satisfying the varying requirements of different residential communities.

Previous research on society management software has mainly focused on evaluating the software's usability and efficiency. The following are some society management software:

A. *No Broker Hood*

A software named No Broker Hood is developed to offer numerous innovative features to simplify everyday chores. It has several unique features visitor management, Bill Payment, Complaint Management [2].

B. *ADDA*

Over 3500 apartment communities worldwide utilize the ADDA apartment or housing society management software. The Apartment Association MC Members can use it to manage society accounting, billing, spending tracking, handle helpdesk tickets, interact with residents internally and more [3].

C. *My Society Club*

You can use features like an online bill management system with My Society Club's cloud accounting solution. Administrators may quickly create maintenance bills for resident members and send them to the members with just one click, making it simple for members to pay their dues online [4].

D. *Apna Complex Platform*

For tenants, management committee members and security personnel, it is the ideal way to make apartment complex living enjoyable and practical [5].

E. *My Gate*

A community management tool that makes life easier for everyone—from residents and management committee members to security personnel and facility managers—in a gated community. With its wealth of capabilities, it streamlines several chores—authorizing entry of delivery executives, paying maintenance bills, using home service, and raising a ticket to the facility manager—into a single click [6].

III. LIMITATION OF EXISTING SYSTEMS

These app/websites have been researched to explore the limitation of existing software management software and propose solutions to address the limitation. Most of the software either operate through a website or an app and not both. Assets which are an integral part of the society such as swimming pool, basketball court, cricket turf etc. should be included in the software for booking purposes. They also fall short in providing verified emergency contacts including contacts of plumbers, AC service providers, Police Station, BMC Helpline Number, Ambulance Services etc. Some systems also do not include individual reports of members tracking their expenses and the overall activities they perform on the app. No other website involves uploading documents on the system such as light bills, gas bills, courier acknowledgement in order to store it digitally in case they get misplaced. Unique logins should be provided for members, admin, and security so that it aims to provide a hassle-free software. Users of society management software, society management businesses, and the general public will all be affected by this research in major ways. By making society management software more approachable and user-friendly

for non-technical people, the study's findings may contribute to an improvement in user experience.

IV. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed system provides a website for the people living in a society to ease the process of managing various activities and events. The software can store the data of various flat owners and their family members. The system needs an administrator to input various flat owner data and billing amounts into it. The system consists of an automatic bill generation facility. It calculates various associated costs, adds them up and provides a bill accordingly.

Our application consists of different modules namely Admin Login, Staff Members, Member Login, Gatekeeper Login, Member Registration and Apartment FAQ Page.

Every module has different functionalities as per the rights given to that person for secure and hassle-free use of the application.

A. *Admin Login:*

The Admin Login module consists of Dashboard which specifies the check ins and checkouts data count [1], event calendar with marked upcoming events, count specifier of the number of residents residing, Gatekeepers on duty and number of Staff members. The Residential Unit consists of the data about the apartments existing in the society that can be more helpful for the filtering purpose later.

The User Management section consists of all the information about the Members, Staff Members, Accountant, Gatekeepers and Committee members like their login details, personal information like Name, Email id, Phone number, etc. Documents is the unique feature which is basically a place where the members can upload all the required and useful documents so that it can be accessed and used in future easily and without any hassle.[2]

Our application also provides a section named Complaints where the admin can see all the complaints posted by the members from their end and can keep the members updated regarding the progress of the problem being resolved. The admin can change the status of the complaint being posted and keep the members updated. The admin also has a right to manage the Parking system by assigning slots to the members if not allocated. The admin can also see the slots status whether it is empty or allocated. He can also manage the visitors and can also add the Notices of anything important or any events.

The admin has the rights to view, update and delete the assets and inventories as per the booked schedule of it [4]. He will have access to all the previous payment history of all the residents, its invoice, charges if any previous backlog of the resident gets applied.

B. Member Login:

The Society Members get to see the similar dashboard, it's just that the residents don't get any extra rights of managing anything. The Member Login module consists of Dashboard which specifies the check ins and checkouts data count, event calendar with marked upcoming events, count specifier of the number of residents residing, Gatekeepers on duty and number of Staff members.

The Residential Unit consists of the data about the apartments existing in the society that can be more helpful for the filtering purpose later. The user can also see the User Management section consisting of all the information about the Members, Staff Members, Accountant, Gatekeepers and Committee members like their login details, personal information like Name, Email id, Phone number, etc. [2]. Documents is the unique feature which is basically a place where the members can upload all the required and useful documents so that it can be accessed and used in future easily and without any hassle.

The members can add documents from their side for future use, post complaints if any, view the notices about the events planned, can book the assets and inventories available in the society booking services and facilities as per the convenience, download the invoice of the paid maintenance and see the Reports of their activity on a timely basis.

C. Gatekeeper Login:

The Gatekeeper also has access to the application with the facility of managing the visitor [1]. He can also manage the Parking of the society based on the allocation of the vehicles of the residents. Whenever a new impromptu visitor arrives, the gatekeeper firstly verifies it with the residents at whose place the visitor must visit [2]. After the verification process, the gatekeeper takes up the entry of the visitor's information like name, phone number, email, check-in time, etc. and then lets in the visitor.

Includes an example of most of the features included in the admin login, member login and security login.

V. CONCLUSION

Overall, Society Sync is an innovative and powerful society management software that has transformed the way residential communities are managed. It is a vital tool for both society management firms and their customers because of its user-friendly design, cutting-edge security features, and customizable features. Residents can benefit from a more efficient, secure, and joyful way of life thanks to Society Sync, while management businesses can work more effectively and give their customers better service.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Mayank Thacker, Lay Shah, Manan Shah, Society sync – Digitalize society management systems with artificial intelligence technologies,
- [2]. Intelligent Systems with Applications, Volume 14, 2022, 200069, ISSN 2667-3053, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iswa.2022.200069>.
- [3]. No Broker Hood Website - <https://www.nobrokerhood.com/>
- [4]. ADDA Website - <https://adda.io/>
- [5]. My Society Club - <https://mysocietyclub.com/>
- [6]. Apna Complex Website - <https://www.apnacomplex.com/>
- [7]. My Gate App - <https://mygate.com/>

Fig 1: Architectural view of Society Sync Dashboard